

SIMULATION OF FABRIC DEFORMATION UNDER MOLDING PROCESS

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Abstract

Fast grown applications of net shape composite demand a fundamental understanding of composite manufacturing process: a near-net shape fabric preform is formed by a weaving process; it is then processed into a composite part by resin transfer molding; extra edges are then removed to obtain a net shape composite component. A computer tool based on dynamic digital element approach is developed to simulate the corresponding fabric micro- and macro- geometries derived from those processes. Firstly, a 3-D woven near-net shape fabric preform is modeled, in which specific boundary conditions are applied and numerical results are verified with experimental results. Secondly, the subsequent molding process is simulated, in which mold surface, mold-fabric contact, and dynamic molding procedure are respectively addressed. At the end, macro- and micro- geometries of both the molded fabric and the net-shape component are observed.

1 Introduction

With the merits of inherent toughness, weight savings and reduced debulking, the 3-D woven fabric has greatly shown its potential in the composite industry. In composite manufacturing process, a fabric is firstly built by weaving the yarns together through specific patterns and then consolidated into a composite component, by resin, within a molding process. Composite manufacturing requires a computer tool to simulate the fabric micro- and macro- geometry determined by the textile weaving process and the subsequent deforming process.

Research into the micro-geometry of uniform fabric derived from weaving process has yielded adoptable results by analyzing the fabric unit cell micro-geometry at both the yarn-level [1][2] and the fiber-level [3]-[5]. At the yarn-level analysis, yarn path is defined by weaving pattern and yarn cross-section is generally assumed to be regular shapes, e.g. ellipse or lenticile. At the fiber-level analysis, yarn shape is defined by the fiber arrangement within that yarn. Fabric is built by assembling the unit cells modeled at either the yarn-level or the fiber-level. However, non-uniform fabrics are often weaved for specific purposes. They do not contain unit cell and usually present complex fabric structure throughout the whole fabric. Then the fabric micro-geometry and macro- geometry have to be investigated based on the whole fabric itself.

Fabric deformability is often studied after a fabric preform model is built. Researchers have had difficulties in modeling the fabric micro-geometry at a full scale, so they have adopted greatly simplified models. Current models in analyzing fabric deformability can be classified into two groups: geometric model and mechanical model. The geometric model describes the fabric using the pin-jointed fishnet model and geometrically maps it to specific surfaces [6][7]. It is fast and efficient but ignores the mechanical phenomenon, such as wrinkling and slippage. The mechanical model takes into consideration the fabric mechanical properties and describes the fabric using finite element models. It is classified into two primary groups: continuous model and discrete model. In the former, fabric is treated as a continuum, modeled by finite shell elements [8][9]. In the latter, each yarn is modeled individually, either by spring elements [10] or shell elements [11]. Since the discrete model takes into account the yarn-to-yarn interaction, it is more

accurate than the continuous model. However, detailed yarn shape has still been neglected. Recently, Taviana et al. [12] used transversely isotropic elastic model to represent a yarn and defined yarn cross-section shape through experimental observation. 2-D woven fabrics were studied. This method has provided fairly good results of fabric deformation. Unfortunately, experimental investigation is not a robust way to obtain the initial yarn shape and fabric micro-geometry and it is also time consuming. In addition, the regular yarn cross-section shape that has been assumed is not applicable to complex fabric geometries, most of which present variable cross-section shapes along a yarn [13][14].

Those assumptions of a fabric in analyzing the fabric deformability have become progressively accurate, but still could not realistically reflect the mechanical behaviors during the fabric deforming process. As it is known that a fabric consists of a number of yarns and each yarn is a bundle of fibers, so the fabric macro- and micro- geometry and the relevant properties are ultimately determined by fiber arrangement in each yarn. Hence, describing a fabric at the fiber-level would be the most attractive choice with today's computer power.

The digital element approach (DEA), a fiber-level based method, has been successfully used to determine the micro-geometry of uniform fabric by accurately modeling fabric unit cell structure [15]-[17]. This method represents a yarn by a number of fibers and each fiber as an assembly of rod elements connected by frictionless joints. Fiber movement is determined by the external and internal forces applied to the fabric. Fiber arrangement in each yarn reflects the fabric micro-geometry. The numerical procedure used in this method has gone through several stages, quasi-static [3][15], static [4], and the latest dynamic algorithm [5][16][17]. The simulation speed has been dramatically increased and the accuracy has been gracefully guaranteed. In this paper, a computer tool based on the dynamic digital element approach is developed to simulate the micro- and macro- geometry of the full field fabric preform and the deformed fabric. This opens a door to analyze a full field fabric at the fiber level.

This paper is organized into three sections: 1) micro- and macro- geometry of 3-D woven near-net shape fabric; 2) simulation of the molding process; and 3)

macro- and micro- geometry of molded fabric. In the first section, the dynamic algorithm is employed to simulate the near-net shape fabric with corresponding boundary conditions applied, and numerical results are validated with experimental investigation. In the second section, several key issues are studied: mesh of mold surface, nodal force calculation, and dynamic molding procedure. In the last section, macro- and micro- geometries of both the molded fabric and the net-shape component are investigated.

2 Micro- and Macro- Geometry of 3-D Woven Near-net Shape Fabric

For the uniform fabric that presents periodic feature, only the micro-geometry of its unit cell needs to be modeled, with periodic boundary conditions applied [5][17]. Fabric is then built by assembling the unit cells together. However, fabrics with complex patterns often need to be designed to meet specific requirements. The 3-D woven near-net shape fabric is one of those structures. At the macro-level, fabric presents a shape near to the final composite component. At the micro-level, yarn shape and yarn-to-yarn interaction are described by fiber arrangements in each yarn. In order to accurately reflect the fabric geometry at both macro- and micro- levels, a full field relaxation process must be conducted based on the fiber-level analysis.

2.1 Boundary Conditions

A fabric is often woven as a single component from a dynamic weaving process [18]. In a typical weaving process, firstly the shuttle takes a weft yarn and moves across the weaving loom, then warp yarns move either upward or downward to interlace the weft yarns. Then a fabric with any specific pattern can be created. A schematic description of fabric structure is shown in Fig. 1, where weft ends are connected and warps interlace wefts in the orthogonal direction.

In simulation of the 3-D woven near-net shape fabric, boundary conditions that respect the actual weaving boundary are applied, as seen in Fig. 2-a. Weft ends are connected correspondingly to form the global fibers. Those settings are also able to stop the warps lateral movements.

Fig. 1 Schematic description of fabric structure

(b) Front view

Fig. 2 Boundary conditions

During the relaxation process, fibers move towards the directions where the minimum potential energy can be reached. As seen in Fig. 2-b, warps ends are open and wefts tend to move laterally. Since fiber-to-fiber frictions are not considered, those wefts may move out of the fabric domain. Thus, virtual boundary walls are set at both ends of the warps to block the wefts lateral movements.

(a) Side view

2.2 3-D Woven Near-net Shape Fabric Preform

In dynamic digital element approach, the primary procedures include [17]: establishing the fabric topology based on textile weaving pattern, applying the digital element mesh, setting up boundary conditions and conducting the dynamic relaxation process. Numerical simulation of the near-net shape fabric preform is shown in Fig. 3.

The preform specimen is woven by Albany Engineered Composites, Inc.. Its length is 13.2 in and width is 3.6 in, it also presents various thicknesses. Various thicknesses are to save the material and reduce the debulking labor when the specimen is made to a composite part. Several typical locations are picked for thickness verification, as seen A, B, C, D, E in the picture. The comparison results are listed in Table 1. In experimental measurement, two different pressures are applied to the fabric, 32 oz and 10 oz. Thicknesses under the pressure of 32 oz are 10~15% smaller than those under the pressure of 10 oz. The latter are also 5~10% smaller than the numerical thicknesses, which are obtained without any pressure applied.

Fig. 3 3-D woven fabric preform

Table 1 Thickness comparison

Location	Numerical thickness (in)	Experimental thickness (in, pressure 10 oz)	Experimental thickness (in, pressure 32 oz)
A	0.155	0.150	0.130
B	0.173	0.160	0.140
C	0.156	0.155	0.140
D	0.169	0.157	0.140
E	0.159	0.160	0.145

In order to investigate the micro-structures, the preform specimen is consolidated by resin and then cut into several pieces, as seen in Fig. 4-a. Micro-structures of cross-sections H-M and H-R of piece H are studied. Good agreements are reached between numerical simulation and experimental observation, as seen in Fig. 4-b and Fig. 4-c, respectively.

(a) The whole sliced specimen

(b) Cross-section H-R

(c) Cross-section H-M

Fig. 4 Micro-structure comparison

3 Simulation of the Molding Process

The near-net shape fabric is then processed to a net shape component through the molding process. Several key issues are addressed: mesh of the mold surface, nodal force calculation, and dynamic molding procedure.

3.1 Mesh of Mold Surface

The mold surface is shown in Fig. 5-a. It must be meshed in order to build contacts with fabric. To facilitate the contact establishment, a standard mesh is proposed. In the standard mesh, the mold surface is discretized into four-node elements, with each element having a square projection on the x-y plane and having an exact size, as seen in Fig. 5-b. The first picture and second picture show the 3-D view and top view of the mold mesh, respectively. The red curve marks the original mold surface and the green box marks the fabric preform domain. It is seen that mold surface has been extended. This is to completely cover the fabric preform so that the boundary irregularities are eliminated during the molding process simulation.

(a) Mold surface

(b) Standard mesh (3-D view and top view)

Fig. 5 Mold surface representation

3.2 Nodal Force Calculation

In digital element approach, forces existing during the molding process include: fiber tensile force, fiber-to-fiber contact force, damping force, fiber-to-fiber friction force, and mold-to-fabric contact force. The first four forces have been presented in previous literatures [13]-[17]. In this paper, the mold-to-fabric contact force will be discussed.

3.2.1 Mold-to-Fabric Contact Force

The mold-to-fabric contact force plays a major role in deforming the fabric. Contact elements are inserted between mold and fabric. In general, contact element length is set around the digital element length which is half of the fiber diameter. A shorter contact element length should be accompanied with larger contact element stiffness to create a reasonable contact force. But this setting has two disadvantages: establishing an exact contact element from each node on fabric to mold surface is inefficient; larger contact element stiffness may incur simulation instability. Thus, fairly long contact element length and relatively small contact element stiffness are adopted. This allows quicker mold movement with the simulation stability assured. Referring to Fig. 6-a, the mold surface has a low curvature and contact element is fairly long, hence contact element can be represented by the vertical

distance between node i and the mold surface, l , rather than the exact distance l' .

As mentioned earlier, each square element on x-y plane is a projection of the corresponding mold element. Referring to Fig. 6-b, for node i on the fabric, the square element it falls into can be quickly identified through its projection (point j') on x-y plane, the element $1'-2'-3'-4'$. Then the corresponding mold element can be easily located, the element $1-2-3-4$. Node i contacts the mold element $1-2-3-4$ at point j . The contact element length is then calculated by

$$l = N_1 z_1 + N_2 z_2 + N_3 z_3 + N_4 z_4 \quad (1)$$

where z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4 are the vertical distances between node i and four nodes of the mold element $1-2-3-4$, respectively. N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4 are the shape functions that can be calculated on the x-y plane respectively by

$$\begin{aligned} N_1 &= \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{2\Delta x}{a}\right) \left(1 - \frac{2\Delta y}{a}\right), \\ N_2 &= \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + \frac{2\Delta x}{a}\right) \left(1 - \frac{2\Delta y}{a}\right), \\ N_3 &= \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + \frac{2\Delta x}{a}\right) \left(1 + \frac{2\Delta y}{a}\right), \\ N_4 &= \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{2\Delta x}{a}\right) \left(1 + \frac{2\Delta y}{a}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where a is the element length of $1'-2'-3'-4'$, Δx and Δy are the distances between point j' and the center of this square element (point o) on x-y plane.

Mold-to-fabric contact force is then calculated as:

$$F_m = k_m \Delta l \quad (3)$$

where k_m is mold-to-fabric contact element stiffness, and Δl is the contact element shortening at each simulation step.

(a) 2-D view

(b) 3-D view

Fig. 6 Mold-to-fabric contact

(a) Initial settings

(b) Final balanced positions

(c) Finished product

Fig. 7 Dynamic molding process

3.3 Dynamic Molding Procedure

The dynamic molding process is described in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7-a describes the initial settings. Fabric is placed between two molds, while the top mold is fixed and the bottom one is free to move. Contact elements are set up according to the shortest distance between fabric and each mold. The shortest distance is also the defined contact distance l_0 . If the vertical distance from the node on fabric to mold surface is smaller than defined contact distance, a contact element is inserted.

After the initial settings are set up, bottom mold moves upwards to deform the fabric. During each moving step, the distance from node on fabric to each mold is checked to determine whether a mold-to-fabric contact element needs to be established. Fabric deforms accordingly. Bottom mold continues to move and more and more contact elements are added until the lengths of all contact elements are equal, as seen in Fig. 7-b. At this balanced position, fabric fully conforms to the mold shapes.

Fig. 7-c shows a finished product. It is formed after removing both molds and the corresponding contact elements. Mold-to-fabric friction and resin effect are both neglected in the simulation of this molding process.

4 Macro- and Micro- Geometry of Molded Fabric

Fabric macro-geometry after molding process is shown in Fig. 8-a, where the red curve marks the original mold profile. Fabric has gracefully conformed to the extended mold shapes. It is then trimmed to a net shape fabric component that follows the original mold shapes, as seen in the Fig. 8-b. The net shape fabric component is then sliced at section A-A. As shown in Fig. 8-c, this deformed fabric presents a various thickness at different locations. This design has greatly reduced the debulking labor and kept the inherent structural toughness to yield a net shape component in the manufacturing process. A local view of the sliced section A-A, section A'-A', is shown in Fig. 8-d. Every digital yarn is represented by 14 digital fibers.

Fig. 8 Fabric macro- and micro- geometries

Conclusion

Researchers have had difficulties to accurately model a full scale fabric and simulate the fabric deformability, so they have employed great model simplifications. As fabric macro- and micro-geometry and the relevant properties are ultimately determined by fiber arrangement in each yarn. Analyzing the fabric deformability at the fiber-level

will be able to provide realistic mechanical behaviors.

Dynamic digital element approach, a fiber-level based approach, has been employed to simulate the fabric unit cell micro-geometry. In this paper, it was used to explore the micro- and macro- geometry of the non-uniform fabric. The 3-D woven near-net shape fabric preform and the net shape fabric were both kindly simulated. The corresponding issues were respectively introduced. The potential of

dynamic digital element approach in simulating the large scale fabric and the corresponding fabric deformability was demonstrated.

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